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Multiple Emulsions for the Co-delivery of Simvastatin and Alendronate Sodium: Improvement in Pharmacokinetic Profile and Oral Therapeutic Efficacy

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Introduction: Blooming of nanocarriers that deliver efficient co-delivery of immiscible hydrophilic/ hydrophobic drugs with conventional technology for industrial invention is critical. Due to such reason, multiple emulsions (MEs) were choosing as required carriers to accomplish the co-delivery capability of various drugs and the enhancement of cancer therapeutic effect. MEs could capture the drug in the inner oil phase and escape the leaking of drug and co-deliver the drugs into the tumor sites (1). Therefore, in the current study, an effort is taken to develop w/o/w multiple emulsions for co-delivery of lipophilic Simvastatin (SVS) and hydrophilic Alendronate Sodium (ADS) with improved oral pharmacokinetics (2).

Methods: MEs were formulated by the use of Poloxamer-407, TPGS and Soyabean Oil. Tween 80 and Span 80 were used as surfactant and co-surfactant correspondingly. The MEs was prepared by the process of primary and secondary emulsification and evaluated in terms of visual assessment, turbidity, viscosity, particle size and zeta potential. The optimized batch was evaluated in terms of TEM analysis, X-Ray diffraction, FTIR study, In-Vitro release and screened for cytotoxicity study, cell cycle arresting, apoptosis study and quantification of SVS and ADS in Rat Plasma.

Results & Discussions: The TEM analysis of optimized batch revealed the formation of spherical shape system and uniform size. X-Ray diffraction study revealed absence of obvious peaks which represents the drug is in amorphous form. SVS and ADS in SEDDS showed narrow release pattern as compared with plain drugs by which simultaneous delivery of both the drugs can be achieved. The MEs treatment retards the cell growth with short IC50 value besides every cell. The AUC in case of ADS and SVS was found to be 710.01 ng/mL and 14.413 ng/mL respectively by oral administration and 42.308 ng/mL and 28.902 ng/mL in 12 and 1 hr respectively by IV administration.

Conclusions: This strategy has improved simultaneous oral bioavailability of very poorly bio-available both ADS and SVS and thus improved the oral therapeutic efficacy of this combination therapy.

Keywords: Alendronate Sodium, Simvastatin, In-vivo Pharmacokinetic Study, Apoptosis Study, Cell cycle Analysis, Cytotoxicity study

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